

COUPLED MULTI-FIELD LINEAR RESPONSE OF TWO-PHASE COMPOSITES: EXACT UNIVERSAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The linear-response moduli of a composite made of two isotropic components must obey a number of compatibility relations, involving the moduli of the components, but totally independent of the mixture ratio of the components and the microstructure of the composite. These compatibility conditions take the form: $C(L, L_a, L_b) \equiv LL_a^{-1}L_b - L_bL_a^{-1}L = 0$, where L_a, L_b are the response matrices of the components, and L is that of the composite. When the composite itself is isotropic, these constitute $n(n-1)/2$ relations that its moduli must obey (for real response matrices), leaving only n independent coefficients to be specified— n being the number of driving fields. When the composite is anisotropic, the elements of L are spatial tensors and the same conditions apply as relations between these tensors. In the latter case one can eliminate the moduli of the components, and obtain relations that the moduli of the composite must satisfy among themselves. The mere fact that the composite is made of two isotropic components imposes strong relations among its moduli, without any further information. For example, we show that all the tensor moduli of such a composite must be symmetric. The same compatibility conditions must also be obeyed by the response matrices of any three composites of the same two isotropic components; so, knowledge of the moduli of two composites supplies constraints on any third, or, for that matter, on the components themselves. The compatibility conditions are of significance only for systems with cross coefficients; otherwise, they are identities.

I. INTRODUCTION

There exists a large body of results on the effective properties of composites made of components with known moduli (e.g. ref 1). These pertain mostly to the uncoupled linear-response properties

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such as the dielectric and permeability constants; or the heat, and electric conductivity. Much of the present knowledge is in the form of bounds on the moduli of the composite—given the volume fraction of the components, and allowing for arbitrary microstructures whereby macroscopic pieces of the components are intermixed to form the composite. Early variational bounds² has been greatly extended to include, for example, anisotropic components and composites (see e.g. ref. 3), and complex moduli^{4,5}.

We concern ourselves here with the moduli of coupled linear-response phenomena, in which the application of one driving force induces not only its own associate flux but also other fluxes. Some examples are: the magneto-electric effect, which is an equilibrium phenomenon, and, on the other hand, dissipation or flow phenomena such as the thermoelectric effect, and the coupled diffusion of particles of different species. We use a unified treatment for both types of phenomena.

Consider a linear-response problem, in a space of arbitrary dimension, d , involving n driving fields, derivable from potentials $\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n)$, and the vector of fluxes $\vec{F} = (\vec{F}_1, \vec{F}_2, \dots, \vec{F}_n)$. We assume that the material is isotropic.

The system possesses a generating function:

$$G \equiv \frac{1}{2} \sum L_{km} \vec{\nabla} \phi_k \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi_m = \frac{1}{2} \sum \vec{F}_i \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi_i, \quad (1)$$

where L is the $n \times n$ response matrix (which is, in general, position dependent). We assume first that L is real.

In the equilibrium case G is some energy function (such as the free energy) that is a functional of the degrees of freedom, ϕ , of the problem. By virtue of the structure of G , L is a symmetric matrix, and for the equilibrium to be stable, L must also be positive definite. For dissipative processes, G is the entropy generation function, (e.g. ref 6) so the second law dictates that L is positive. The Onsager reciprocity relations (see e.g. ref 6) amount to the symmetry of L (with a few exceptions that we disregard here). The fluxes are the conjugates of the potentials:

$$F_{k\alpha} = \frac{\partial G}{\partial (\partial_\alpha \phi_k)}, \quad (2)$$

where α is a space-coordinate index. The field equations are:

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{F} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (L \vec{\nabla} \phi) = 0, \quad (3)$$

which are the Euler-Lagrange equations for the equilibrium case and express the conservation of the currents in the (steady state) dissipative case.

We shall be interested in two-phase composites in which L takes the value of the pure component within each grain. The field equation can then be solved, in principle, by solving the Laplace equations, $\Delta \phi_k = 0$, within each region, with the boundary conditions: (i) The potentials ϕ_k are continuous across boundaries, and (ii) The component of the fluxes perpendicular to the boundary is continuous.

II. THE COMPATIBILITY RELATIONS

Consider two isotropic substances, a and b with their response matrices L_a, L_b respectively. The L 's are real, symmetric, and positive-definite.

Such matrices can be diagonalize simultaneously⁷ by a real matrix W such that:

$$WL_a\tilde{W} = \lambda^a = \text{diag}(\lambda_1^a, \lambda_2^a, \dots, \lambda_n^a); \quad WL_b\tilde{W} = \lambda^b = \text{diag}(\lambda_1^b, \lambda_2^b, \dots, \lambda_n^b). \quad (4)$$

Now, if we work with the eigenbasis that consists of the potentials and fluxes:

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1}\phi, \quad J = WF, \quad (5)$$

the response matrices in the two substances are given by λ^a and λ^b . We have $\sum \vec{J}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi_k = \sum \vec{F}_k \cdot \vec{\nabla} \phi_k$, so, the generating function remains the same. The field equations in the eigenbasis remain of the same form: $\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\lambda \vec{\nabla} \psi) = 0$. Since the eigenfields are totally decoupled in both components, they are decoupled also in the composite; in other words, the effective response matrix of the composite must also be diagonal in this basis:

$$WL\tilde{W} = \lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n). \quad (6)$$

All the information on the volume fractions of the components and the microstructure of the composite enters through the constants λ_i .

Obviously, λ, λ^a , and λ^b all commute. This fact can be cast in forms that involve only L, L_a , and L_b but not W . Writing:

$$\lambda(\lambda^a)^{-1}\lambda^b - \lambda^b(\lambda^a)^{-1}\lambda = 0, \quad (7)$$

we get:

$$C(L, L_a, L_b) \equiv LL_a^{-1}L_b - L_bL_a^{-1}L = 0. \quad (8)$$

These are the compatibility conditions that L must satisfy to qualify as a response matrix of an isotropic composite.

The same arguments apply for the response matrices of any three composites made of the same two components. Their representations in the eigenbasis J, ψ must all commute, so in the original, "physical" fields, F, ϕ , they must satisfy the compatibility conditions. Thus, it is enough to measure the response matrices of two composites to provide constraints on any third (including any of the two components)

The compatibility conditions must apply also when the problem can be formulated in terms of complex fields and the response matrix is Hermitian. When the response matrix is complex and symmetric this is also true except for a set of measure zero of response matrices.

The compatibility conditions enjoy some very useful symmetries and superposition properties.

(1) The conditions $C(L, L_a, L_b) = 0$ are symmetric in L_a and L_b . In fact, they are totally symmetric with respect to the three arguments of C . Knowledge of any two of the three cast constraints on the third.

(2) The conditions are satisfied automatically for $L = L_a$ and $L = L_b$.

(3) When the three arguments are diagonal, the compatibility conditions are identities, so we have nothing to add to our knowledge of such systems.

(4) If two matrices commute, and the third is compatible with them, the latter must also commute with them.

(5) If three matrices are compatible, so are their inverses.

(6) If matrices L_1, L_2, \dots are compatible with L_a and L_b , so is any linear or harmonic combination of them, i.e. any matrix of the forms $\sum \nu_i L_i$, or $(\sum \nu_i L_i^{-1})^{-1}$ (ν_i are numbers). Thus, the combination of mixtures that are compatible with two components, in series or in parallel, produces another one that is also compatible with them.

III. ANISOTROPIC COMPOSITES

For arbitrary anisotropic materials exhibiting a coupled linear-response phenomenon in d space dimensions, the relations between potentials and fluxes are:

$$F_{k\alpha} = \sum_{m\beta} L_{km\alpha\beta} \partial_\beta \phi_m. \quad (9)$$

Latin indices designate the field type, as before; Greek indices designate space coordinates: $\alpha, \beta = 1, \dots, d$. The response matrix is symmetric with respect to the simultaneous exchange of both: $L_{km\alpha\beta} = L_{mk\beta\alpha}$. For a fixed pair of fields, ϕ_k, ϕ_m , $T(km)$ are the tensor moduli (the $\alpha\beta$ element of which is $L_{km\alpha\beta}$). The T 's are, in general, asymmetric, unless $k = m$, in which case the symmetry of L dictates that they are.

Now, in the eigenbasis J, ψ , the response matrix of an anisotropic composite does not connect fields ψ_k , and ψ_m , with $k \neq m$, and must be of the form:

$$\lambda_{km\alpha\beta} = t_{\alpha\beta}^k \delta_{km}. \quad (10)$$

Thus, the $d^2, n \times n$ matrices $\ell(\alpha\beta)$ formed from L by fixing the space indices, are diagonal in this basis. This means that a. Each of the $\ell(\alpha\beta)$ must obey the compatibility conditions with L_a, L_b ; resulting in d^2 sets of compatibility conditions. Put differently, the compatibility conditions must be obeyed when we substitute for the elements L_{km} of L in eq.(8), the tensors $T(km)$. b. Any three of $\ell(\alpha\beta)$ must satisfy the compatibility conditions among themselves, just as any three composite response matrices must. In such relations, the moduli of the components do not appear, and we are left with relations.

$$C[\ell(\alpha\beta), \ell(\gamma\delta), \ell(\epsilon\eta)] = 0, \quad (11)$$

for all the choices of the six space indices (not all of these relations are independent). One then obtains the surprising result that the tensor moduli of the composite must obey, among themselves, relations that require no knowledge of the composites (except that they are isotropic) nor of the mixture ratio or the microstructure of the composite. As a special case of these relations we find that the tensor moduli of such a composite must all be symmetric tensors.

IV. EXAMPLES FOR TWO-FIELD SYSTEMS

For two field-systems whose response matrices are:

$$L_i = \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_i & \alpha_i \\ \alpha_i & \mu_i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

there is only one compatibility relation for the effective coefficients, ε, μ, α :

$$\begin{vmatrix} \varepsilon & \mu & \alpha \\ \varepsilon_1 & \mu_1 & \alpha_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 & \mu_2 & \alpha_2 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad (13)$$

exhibiting the symmetry of the condition in the three materials.

We have verified this relation for the coated sphere composite² by direct calculations of the magneto-electric coefficients. The effective constants, which are rather cumbersome functions of the volume-ratio of the two components and of their constants, satisfy eq.(13).

When the composite is anisotropic, eq.(13) should hold with ε, μ, α being space tensors. We have calculated the tensor moduli for a diluted mixture of triaxial ellipsoids in vacuum and verified that the tensor response coefficient of the composite satisfy eq.(13). In this case, as well as in the general case of any anisotropic composite with orthorhombic symmetry, there is a component-independent relation which the effective moduli must satisfy:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \varepsilon_{zz} & \mu_{zz} & \alpha_{zz} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} & \mu_{yy} & \alpha_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} & \mu_{zz} & \alpha_{zz} \end{vmatrix} = 0; \quad (14)$$

the tensor moduli of the dilute-ellipsoid composite satisfy this relation.

REFERENCES

1. G. W. Milton, in *Homogenization and Effective Moduli of Materials and Media*, Eds, J.L. Ericksen, et.al., Springer, New York (1986).
2. Z. Hashin and S. Shtrikman, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **33**, 3125 (1962).
3. G. W. Milton and R.V. Kohn, Preprint (1988); R.V. Kohn and G. W. Milton in *Homogenization and Effective Moduli of Materials and Media*, Eds. J.L. Ericksen, et.al., Springer, New York, (1986).
4. G. W. Milton, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **52**, 5286 (1981).
5. D. J. Bergman, *Annals of Physics*, **138**, 78 (1982).
6. H. B. Callen, *Thermodynamics*, John Wiley, New York, (1960).
7. This procedure is the same as that used to diagonalize simultaneously the kinetic and potential-energy tensors in a problem of small oscillations near an equilibrium, where the tensors are also symmetric and positive definite.